

Evaluation of Some Haematological Parameters in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer in Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract

Prostate cancer is a leading cause of mortality among aged men and the burden of disease has a significant impact on the quality of life of men affected by the disease. The aim of this study was to evaluate some haematological parameters (PCV, Hb, WBC, platelet) in prostate cancer attending Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Imo State. The research was a cross-sectional study, carried out at oncology department clinic of FTH Owerri between July-August 2024. All eligible subjects who filled the questionnaire and gave a written informed consent for the study period were sampled. The period of subject enrolment, classification, sample collection and laboratory determination of some haematological parameters in patient diagnosed with prostate cancer lasted from July 2024 to August 2024. The procedure was carried out at the Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, with the results of the tests been analyzed using SPSS version 27. The mean value of haemoglobin (9.68±1.24) g/dl, PCV (28.73±3.38) %, was significantly reduced ($p=0.000$, $p=0.000$, in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to control (14.68±21.79) g/dl, (42.13±2.46) %, The mean value of white blood cell (15.87±5.13) $\times 10^9/L$, platelet (336.17±105.36) $\times 10^9/L$ was significantly increased ($p=0.000$ and $p=0.000$) in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to control. There was a non-significant decrease ($p=0.361$, $p=0.377$, $p=0.714$ and $p=0.428$) in the mean value of haemoglobin (11.01±1.11)g/dl, PCV (37.73±2.75)%, and platelet (235.53±79.01) $\times 10^9/L$ in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer but on treatment when compared to control (14.68±21.79)g/dl, (42.13±2.46)%, (242.80±73.84) $\times 10^9/L$. There was a non-significant increase ($p=0.787$) in the mean value of WBC (9.03±3.74) cells $\times 10^9/L$ in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer but on treatment when compared to control (8.79±2.86) $\times 10^9/L$. There was a non significant positive correlation ($r=0.08$, $p=0.681$; $r=0.01$, $p=0.972$ and $r=0.14$, $p=0.476$) between ferritin with PCV, and RBC in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer. Prostate cancer disease affects the level of haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, platelet, causing a decrease in the level of haemoglobin, PCV, and serum iron coupled with an increase in the level of WBC, platelet count.

Keywords: haematologic, diagnosed, prostate cancer, owerri, imo state.

INTRODUCTION

Prostate cancer (PCa) is the second most common cancer in men worldwide, with an estimated incidence of 1.1 million new cases in 2012 and the sixth most important cancer in the world, and its incidence in blacks has been on the increase in men of 50 years and above [1]

Symptoms unrelated to prostate cancer can be caused by bladder problems, urinary tract infections (UTIs), prostatitis or even cancer of the prostate (PCa). Early diagnosis of a disease is important, because the sooner the disease is detected, the better [2]. The prostate gland is a major secondary endocrine organ of males whose development and growth depends on androgen stimulation especially by dihydrotestosterone (DHT), an active metabolic product from the conversion of testosterone by steroid 5 α -reductase.

Prostate specific antigen (PSA) is a serine protease that is immunologically specific for prostate tissue as opined by Heller. The initiation, development, invasion, and metastasis of a tumor are always accompanied by inflammation and immune response, which have a complex interaction with the tumor microenvironment [3]

In developed countries, carcinoma of the prostate gland is more prevalent in the elderly male population compared with younger men. Around 15% of men diagnosed to have cancer of the prostate in the developed world when compared to only about 4% of men in emerging nations [4]. While, many men present with localized and potentially curable disease, a large number of deaths from prostate cancer is due to the development of metastatic disease. Therefore, more accurate prognosis and predictive markers should be applied for prostate cancer to guide therapy and monitor disease progress in individual patients [5].

Haematological parameters measure the variability and count of circulating blood cells. It is routinely reported to physicians in clinical practice as part of the automated complete blood count and is currently mainly used as an index in the differential diagnosis of anemia [6] Recently, studies have demonstrated that haematological parameters might provide useful information for the prognosis of patients with cardiovascular diseases, heart failure, coronary artery diseases, and chronic heart disease. Although the underlying biological mechanisms remain understand. Haematological parameters have been recognized as a global marker of chronic inflammation and oxidative stress. Various studies have reported that cancer affects haematological parameters such as a reduction in mean haemoglobin (Hb), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean cell haemoglobin (MCH), and mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) and an increase in red cell distribution width (RCDW) [7]

Iron is the first and the most important trace element in cellular metabolism. It occurs at many metabolic mechanisms including the modulation of the immune system and more particularly in the production of hemoglobin by the process of erythropoiesis [8]. Ferritin is a universal intracellular protein that stores iron and releases it in a controlled fashion, while transferrins are involve in the transport of iron [9]. Iron metabolism control occurs at the level of the body to maintain the stock of iron and its distribution to adequate levels, but also at the cellular level, thereby ensuring optimal biological functions [10]. Iron deficiency is the cause of various metabolic disorders whose final stage is anemia. The concentration of serum iron and the iron-binding protein, transferrin, varies markedly in different pathological and physiological conditions. Both concentrations (with transferrin being expressed as total iron-binding capacity) with or without serum ferritin are used in identifying various types of anaemia [11]

Prostate cancer is a leading cause of mortality among aged men and the burden of disease have a significant impact on the quality of life of men affected by the disease [12]. Reports on the high incidence of prostate cancer in humans and their influence on the quality of life of patients have made a search for the most reliable diagnostic tool to aid their treatment a priority for public health (Nutting *et al.*, 2017). The highest rate of incidence has been observed in Africa, at least partially due to the widespread use of prostate-specific antigen (PSA) testing. Humphrey, (2020) has estimated that the percentage of patients with a low risk of progression is between 50% and 60% of newly diagnosed cases. Thus, the early diagnosis of prostate cancer can play a key role in the reduction of the risk and complications associated with the disease, and the level of haematological parameters and iron status can be a diagnostic tool. The result from this study will play a significant role in the management of the disease as knowledge on the level of some haematological and biochemical parameters will aid early diagnosis and treatment of the disease.

In developed countries, carcinoma of the prostate gland is more prevalent in the elderly male population compared with younger men. Around 15% of men diagnosed to have cancer of the prostate in the developed world when compared to only about 4% of men in emerging nations [13]

Recent studies have implicated haematological parameters in the pathogenesis of prostate cancer [14]. There is paucity of information on haematological parameters in patients with prostate cancer in Owerri, therefore the study is aimed at evaluating haematological parameters in prostate cancer patient.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted at the Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH), Owerri, Imo state.

Study Design

The research was a cross-sectional study, carried out at oncology department clinic of FTH Owerri between July-August 2024. All eligible subjects who filled the questionnaire and gave a written informed consent for the study period were sampled. The period of subject enrolment, classification, sample collection and laboratory determination of some haematological parameters, in patient diagnosed with prostate cancer lasted from July 2024 to August 2024.

Method of Recruitment

A total of one hundred and fifty subjects were selected, which comprises of fifty (50) patients confirmed of suffering from prostate cancer due to high PSA level and histological examination of the tissue samples from the prostate, fifty (50) prostate cancer patients on treatment and fifty (50) healthy males who served as controls were recruited for the study. The study participants were given an informed consent form. Subjects who agreed to sign the informed consent form were recruited for the study and were given a structured questionnaire to fill.

Sample Collection

Ten milliliters (2 mls) of venous blood sample was collected at the ante-cubital vein aseptically, 2ml was dispensed into Ethylene di-amine tetra acetic acid container, for determining some haematological parameters,

Ethical Consideration

The research proposal was submitted and ethical approval was obtained from Chairman Ethics Committee of Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri. All study participants who were given consent were enrolled in this study and samples was taken.

Selection criteria

Inclusion criteria

- i) Patient suffering from Prostate cancer (On treatment and not on treatment)
- ii) Patients who gave their informed consent
- iii) Those without any other infection such as HIV, HBsAg, HCV, Syphilis etc.
- iv) Age-matched subjects without prostate cancer who served as controls.

Exclusion criteria

- i) Patients who did not give their informed consent were excluded from the study.
- ii) Those with other infections such as HIV, HCV, HBsAg, syphilis etc.

3.7 Sample Size Determination

Araoye formula for calculating sample size was used in this study.

$$N = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2}$$

N=desired sample size

Z= the standard normal deviate usually set at 1.96

P= the proportion of the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic at 95% confidence. P is set at 0.033 (WHO, 2020).

q=1-p

d= degree of accuracy set at 0.05

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.07 \times (1-0.07)}{0.05^2} = \frac{3.84 \times 0.07 \times 0.93}{0.0025} = \frac{0.25}{0.0025} = 100$$

Sample size = 100

However, sample size of 100 was used.

Laboratory Procedures

Reagents were commercially purchased and the manufactures operational instructions were followed.

Determination of some hematological parameters (PCV, RBC, WBC, Platelets)

Principle

Automated analyzers often utilize the coulter principle which measures changes in electric impedance as cells pass through a small aperture. The analyzer detects and counts cells based on the size and number of pulses generated as each cell passes through the aperture. The amplified resistance is processed and thereafter processed for interpretation into a histogram by a computer.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 27. Mean, standard deviation, t-test and Pearson correlation were determined. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

4.1 Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer versus Controls

The mean values of haemoglobin (9.68±1.24)g/dl, PCV (28.73±3.38)%, were significantly reduced in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to controls (14.68±21.79)g/dl, (42.13±2.46)%, (t= 4.42, p = 0.000; t = 4.45,).

The mean values of white blood cell (15.87±5.13) x 10⁹/L, platelets (336.17±105.36) x 10⁹/L were significantly increased in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to controls (t = 6.59, p = 0.001; t = 3.98, p = 0.000).

Table 4.1: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer versus Controls (mean ± SD)

Parameter	Prostate cancer patients (n=30)	Healthy Controls (n=30)	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.68±1.24	14.68±21.79	4.42	0.000
PCV (%)	28.73±3.38	42.13±2.46	4.45	0.000
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	15.87±5.13	8.79±2.86	6.59	0.001
Platelet (x 10 ⁹ /L)	336.17±105.36	242.80±73.84	3.98	0.000

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

PCV: Packed cell volume

*: Significant p value

SD: Significant Deviation

4.2 Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer on Treatment versus Control

There was a non-significant decrease in the mean values of haemoglobin (11.01±1.11)g/dl, PCV (37.73±2.75)%, platelet (235.53±79.01) x10⁹/L in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer on treatment when compared to control (14.68±21.79)g/dl, (42.13±2.46)%, (242.80±73.84) x10⁹/L (t = 0.92, p =0.361; t = 0.89, p = 0.377; t = 0.37, p=0.714).

There was a non-significant increase in the mean value of WBC (9.03±3.74) cellsx10⁹/L in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer on treatment when compared to control (8.79±2.86) x10⁹/L(t=0.27, p=0.787).

Table 4.2: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer on Treatment versus Controls (mean ± SD)

Parameter	Prostate cancer patients on treatment (n=30)	Healthy Control (n=30)	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	11.01±1.11	14.68±21.79	0.92	0.361
PCV (%)	37.73±2.75	42.13±2.46	0.89	0.377
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	9.03±3.74	8.79±2.86	0.27	0.787
Platelet (x10 ⁹ /L)	235.53±79.01	242.80±73.84	0.37	0.714

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

PCV: Packed cell volume

*: significant p value

p>0.05: not significant

4.3 Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer versus Prostate Patients Cancer on Treatment

The mean values of haemoglobin (9.68±1.24)g/dl, PCV (28.73±3.38) were significantly reduced in patients diagnosed to prostate cancer when compared with prostate cancer patient on treatment (11.01±1.11)g/dl, (37.73±2.75)%, (14.18±6.75) μmol/L and (47.03±10.74) μmol/L(t= 4.37, p = 0.000; t = 4.28, p = 0.000).

The mean values of WBC (15.87 ± 5.13) $\times 10^9/L$, platelet (336.17 ± 105.36) $\times 10^9/L$ were significantly increased in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to prostate cancer patient on treatment (9.03 ± 3.74) $\times 10^9/L$, (235.53 ± 79.01) $\times 10^9/L$ $p = 0.001$; $t = 4.19$, $p = 0.000$ and $t = 14.78$, $p = 0.000$).

Table 4.3: Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer versus Prostate Cancer Patients on Treatment

Parameter	Prostate cancer patients (n=30)	Prostate cancer patients on treatment (n=30)	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.68 \pm 1.24	11.01 \pm 1.11	4.37	0.000
PCV (%)	28.73 \pm 3.38	37.73 \pm 2.75	5.02	0.000
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	15.87 \pm 5.13	9.03 \pm 3.74	5.90	0.001
Platelet ($\times 10^9/L$)	336.17 \pm 105.36	235.53 \pm 79.01	4.19	0.000

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

PCV: Packed cell volume

4.4 Comparison of the Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer based on Age

There was a non-significant increase in the mean values of haemoglobin (9.96 ± 1.19)g/dl, PCV (29.60 ± 2.67)%, WBC (16.41 ± 4.30) $\times 10^9/L$ and platelets (354.87 ± 106.12) $\times 10^9/L$ in patients of ages (50-65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to patients of ages (>65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer (9.38 ± 1.26)g/dl, (27.73 ± 3.77)%, (14.48 ± 6.20) $\times 10^9/L$ and (299.07 ± 95.52) $\times 10^9/L$ ($t = 1.29$, $p = 0.206$; $t = 1.57$, $p = 0.129$; $t = 0.99$, $p = 0.332$; and $t = 1.51$, $p = 0.141$).

There was a non-significant decrease in the mean value of serum iron (8.24 ± 2.93) $\mu\text{mol/L}$, ferritin (320.67 ± 73.17) ng/ml and TIBC (38.33 ± 6.08) $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in patients of age (50-65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to patients of age (>65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer (9.19 ± 1.6) $\mu\text{mol/L}$, (390.47 ± 79.90) ng/ml and (44.73 ± 10.62) $\mu\text{mol/L}$ ($t = 1.05$, $p = 0.304$; $t = 2.49$, $p = 0.069$ and $t = 2.03$, $p = 0.055$).

Table 4.4: Comparison of the Mean Values of Haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, Platelets, Serum Iron and Ferritin in Patients Diagnosed with Prostate Cancer based on Age. (mean \pm SD)

Parameter	(50-65) yrs	(>65) yrs	t-value	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	9.96 \pm 1.19	9.38 \pm 1.26	1.29	0.206
PCV (%)	29.60 \pm 2.67	27.73 \pm 3.77	1.57	0.129
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	16.41 \pm 4.30	14.48 \pm 6.20	0.99	0.332
Platelet S($\times 10^9/L$)	354.87 \pm 106.12	299.07 \pm 95.52	1.51	0.141
Serum iron ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	8.24 \pm 2.93	9.19 \pm 1.6	1.05	0.304
Ferritin (ng/ml)	320.67 \pm 73.17	390.47 \pm 79.90	2.49	0.069
TIBC ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)	38.33 \pm 6.08	44.73 \pm 10.62	2.03	0.055

KEY:

Hb: Haemoglobin

PCV: Packed cell volume

TIBC: Total iron binding capacity

SD: Significant Deviation

Discussion

Prostate cancer is increasing at alarming rate especially with aging men in Nigeria and the world at large. Prostate cancer is the sixth most important cancer in the world, and its incidence in blacks has been on the increase in men of 50 years and above [15]

In the present study, the mean value of haemoglobin and PCV were significantly reduced in prostate cancer patient when compared to the controls. The decrease could be as a result of the increased PSA level which have a suppressing effect on haemoglobin and PCV which leads to anaemia with low survival rate if not well managed [16]. The result of the study is in agreement with the study carried out by [17], who reported that prostate cancer patients have reduced values of

haemoglobin and PCV which reflect an underlying inflammatory state that can impair erythrocyte maturation and consequent inadequate production of the hormone erythropoietin. They further stated that the inflammatory responses that occurs as a result of a prostate cancer is strongly related to ineffective erythropoiesis, and it has been demonstrated that inflammatory cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , IL-1 β and IL-6, desensitize bone marrow erythroid progenitors to erythropoiesis, inhibit red blood cell (RBC) maturation and thereby promote anisocytosis [18]. From the result of the study, there was no significant difference in the mean values of haemoglobin and PCV in prostate cancer patients on treatment when compared to the healthy control. The result clearly indicates that the treatment regimen administered to patients suffering from prostate cancer helps ameliorate the adverse effect caused by the prostate cancer as the levels of haemoglobin and packed cell volume were significantly increased in prostate cancer patient on treatment when compared to those not on treatment.

From the result of the current study, serum iron was significantly reduced in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to controls. The reduced level of serum iron could be as a result of the increased utilization of iron by the cancer cells which thereby results in its decreased level [19]. The result which is consistent with the report by [19] reveals that in prostate cancer, Tumor-Associated Macrophages (TAM) activity is influenced by chemical signals from tumor cells [20]. One such signal could be the induction of lipocalin 2 (Lp2) secretion, which is why increased Lp2 from TAMs has been proposed as another strategy from cancer cells to provide additional iron for their needs [21] Lp2 is a protein which has a strong binding capacity for iron chelating molecules such as siderophores [22]. It is produced by neutrophils, macrophages, epithelial cells but also by tumor cells [23]. In-vitro and in-vivo data with breast cancer models show that iron-loaded Lp2 produced by TAMs can increase the iron pool of tumor cells, and consequently, influence their growth [24]. The importance of Lp2 in PCa iron metabolism is further enhanced by its frequently observed over expression in PCa which is related with cancer proliferation [25] Furthermore, serum Lp2 has been found in high levels in patients with PCa [26] Still, the details of the TAM-Lip2 connection with PCa cell iron metabolism have not been studied and should be a subject of future studies. Comparison of the mean value of serum iron in patients with prostate cancer but on treatment revealed that there was no significant difference in the value of serum iron in patients on treatment when compared to controls. However the mean value of serum iron was increased in patients on treatment when compared to those not on treatment.

TIBC was significantly reduced in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to controls. The decreased level indicates that prostate cancer causes a reduction in total iron binding capacity, but the exact mechanism is yet known. The finding from this study is in agreement with a study carried out by [26] in America who included 34 patients with prostate cancer and 84 controls, they revealed a lower level of transferrin saturation in patients with prostate cancer than that in controls.

In this study, the mean value of total white blood cell count was significantly increased in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to controls. An increased number of WBC can occur abnormally as a result of inflammation which causes prostatic enlargement [27]. The asymptomatic inflammation that occurs in prostate cancer may increase the WBC and the neutrophil count however, the exact mechanism at which inflammation of the prostate leads to an increase in white blood cells is not fully known [28]. Finding from this study is in agreement with previous studies were it was reported that inflammatory markers were associated with an increased risk of several cancers [29], but the associations with prostate cancer were inconsistent. Furthermore, the associations of intraprostatic inflammation with prostate tumour prognosis remain unclear [30]. There was no significant difference in the mean value of white blood cell count in prostate cancer patients on treatment when compared to those not on treatments. The insignificant difference clearly indicates that the treatment of patients with prostate cancer have a significant effect on the overall health of the patients.

The present study also revealed that the mean value of platelet count was significantly increased in prostate cancer patients when compared to Controls. The pathomechanism of the relationship between solid tumour-associated thrombocytosis and survival is not known. Several hypotheses have been proposed. Platelets may be activated by tumour cells in a process known as the tumour cell-induced platelet aggregation. Platelet activation may occur either by direct interaction with tumour cells, or indirectly, through the mediation of adenosine diphosphate (ADP), thromboxane A₂, or metalloproteinases [31]. Additionally, tumour cells may secrete thrombin, or may stimulate pro-thrombotic activity in other tissues, and can thereby contribute to enhanced platelet activation. Activated platelets facilitate the growth of tumour cells by releasing a number of angiogenic and tumour growth factors. These include thrombospondin, platelet factor 4, transforming growth factor-beta, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), and platelet-derived growth factor [32]. The result of this study is in agreement with the study carried out by [33], who also revealed an increased level of platelet count in patients suffering from prostate cancer. There was a non-significant decrease in the mean value of platelet count in patients diagnosed with prostate cancer on treatment when compared to controls. The non-significant difference is an indication that intensive care received by patients with prostate cancer has a positive effect on the patient. With respect to serum ferritin level, there was a significant increase in its level in prostate cancer patient when compared to controls. However, prostate cancer patient on treatment recorded a decreased level of ferritin when compared to the

healthy controls. The increase in ferritin level might be as a result of the low level of iron recorded in the study. The finding from this study is in agreement with the study carried out [7], who also reported an increase in ferritin level in prostate cancer patients. Ferritin is a hollow protein shell composed of two functionally distinct subunits, namely, H-subunit and L-subunit and capable of storing up to 4500 Fe (III) atoms within a single molecule. H-subunit acts as a ferroxidase that transforms highly toxic Fe (II) to the mild Fe (III) form, thereby enabling ferritin to sequester it in its cavity. Its capability of sequestering free Fe gives ferritin the function of iron detoxification and thus may reduce the incidence of iron overload, causing a decreased risk of prostate cancer [34].

There was no significant difference in the mean value of haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, platelets, serum iron, ferritin and TIBC in patients of age (50-65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer when compared to patients of ages (>65) yrs diagnosed with prostate cancer. The research study focused on the elderly, with the insignificant difference in result confirming that the disease is common in adults from age 45 and above and also causes the same adverse effect [35] The result is consistent with the report revealed by [36,37]

Conclusion

Prostate cancer disease alters the levels of haemoglobin, PCV, WBC, platelet, causing a decrease in the level of haemoglobin, PCV, coupled with an increase in the levels of WBC, platelet count.

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